

INTERFACE CHARACTERISTICS AND AGE HARDENING BEHAVIOUR OF SiC-REINFORCED Al-BASED ALLOYS

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ABSTRACT

The age hardening behaviour of Al-7% Si-0,3% Mg and 6061 alloys containing SiC particles incorporated by the compocasting technique is investigated in this paper. Hardness measurements show that the kinetics of hardening is different in the composite compared to the matrix depending on the aging temperature and is also influenced by the surfacic nature of the particles. Indeed oxidized SiC particles completely suppress age hardening in Al-7% Si-0,3% Mg due to spinel formation at the interface which leads to Mg depletion in the matrix. This effect does not occur in an alloy containing a greater amount of Mg as in the case of 6061, despite the formation of spinel at the interface as identified by transmission electron microscopy observations. These results show that optimization of aging treatments and alloy composition is needed for aluminium matrix composites, particularly if interfacial reactions are taking place during the fabrication process.

INTRODUCTION

Most aluminium-matrix composites are fabricated with age-hardenable alloys and it is now well-known from previous investigations on various systems (B_4C particles/6061 (1), SiC whiskers/6061 (2), SiC whiskers/2124 (3), SiC particles/2014 (4), Al_2O_3 fibres/Al-3,5% Cu (4), SiC particles/Al-7% Si-0,3% Mg (5) that the addition of fibres, whiskers or particles changes the aging response of the matrix, which may lead to a necessary redefinition of the treatment. Moreover, depending on the surfacic nature of the particles and the composition of the matrix, interface reactions can occur leading to some modification of the matrix composition and then to its aging characteristics. This phenomenon was clearly observed recently in Al - 7% Si - 0,3% Mg (AS7G03) containing oxidized SiC particles (6).

The aim of this work is to investigate more deeply the age hardening kinetics at various temperatures of AS7G03 and 6061 alloys containing SiC particles and also to correlate age hardening behaviour and particle-matrix interfaces. For this purpose, non oxidized and oxidized particles were used in both alloys to vary the interface nature. Hardness measurements were performed together with TEM observations for the characterization of the materials after heat treatment.

EXPERIMENTAL

AS7G03 and 6061-alloys were reinforced by SiC particles using the compocasting technique. The same fabrication procedure was employed for both alloys i.e : addition of the particles to the semi-solid alloy, stirring of the melt for 15 min

The temperature affects also the efficiency of the aging treatment which can be defined as the difference between the hardnesses at the peak-aging time and in the solution-treated condition. Comparison between Fig. 1 a,b and c shows that efficiency is higher for the composite than for the matrix alloy at low temperature but the inverse is observed at high temperature as it was already reported in this alloy, the efficiency decreasing further as particle volume fraction increases (5).

The aging behaviour of the composite containing artificially oxidized particles is very different from that of the other composite. For these particles, aging was only carried out at 185°C. Hardness increases only very slightly during the first 30 min of treatment after which it remains constant. The hardness of the composite in the solution-treated condition is, however, the same as that of the composite with non oxidized particles.

The same experiments were performed with the 6061 Al-alloy and the variation with aging time at 175°C and 220°C of the Brinell hardness is shown in Fig. 2 a and b. For this material, as-received and oxidized particles were also used but for the latter, aging was only performed at 175°C. Fig. 2 a and b show that the same aging behaviour as for AS7G03 is observed with as received particles i.e. :

- a decrease of the peak aging time with increasing aging temperature.
- an acceleration of aging at 220°C in the particle reinforced alloy compared to the unreinforced one whereas at 175°C, peak hardness occurs approximately at the same time.

Fig. 2 Aging characteristics of the matrix 6061 and the composites
a) 175°C
b) 220°C

The aging behaviour of the 6061 Al-alloy reinforced with oxidized particles is however completely different from that of the AS7G03 : hardness shows approximately the same evolution with aging time as for as-received particles with however a higher peak hardness at a later aging time by a factor of about 2.

The hardness measurements thus clearly indicate that the temperature and the surfacic nature of the SiC particles greatly influence the aging behaviour of the composites, compared to that of the unreinforced matrix and this influence depends also on the matrix alloy composition. The effects of these parameters will now be discussed with reference to TEM observations of the particle-matrix interfaces.

DISCUSSION

A normal aging behaviour is observed for the composites with as-received particles whatever the temperature and the alloy composition : hardness is higher than that of the matrix in the solution-treated condition and it increases during heat treatment ; also increasing temperature decreases the aging time for maximum aging. However acceleration is observed at high temperature whereas the inverse occurs at low temperature. Acceleration was frequently observed (1-5) and attributed to the thermal mismatch between the SiC particles and the matrix which generates a high dislocation density close to the interfaces and residual stresses. Deceleration was reported by Rack in SiC whiskers /6061 (2) for low temperature aging and by Friend and coworkers (7) who attributed the phenomenon to the inhibition of GP zone formation due to a lack of quenched-in vacancies as for aluminosilicate fibre reinforced Al-Cu (8) and SAP alloys (9-10). A possible cause for the low quenched-in vacancy concentration is vacancy sinking by dislocations produced in the matrix by the thermal mismatch and by particle matrix interfaces. However there is no direct experimental evidence for this explanation.

The aging behaviour of the composites containing oxidized SiC particles depends sharply on the composition of the matrix. In AS7G03, the presence of oxidized particles almost completely suppresses age hardening whereas in 6061, it affects only slightly the aging characteristics compared to as-received particles. This phenomenon is closely related to Mg depletion of the matrix due to spinel formation at the interface (6,7). TEM observations show indeed clear evidence of spinel at the interfaces of both AS7G03/SiC and 6061/SiC composites (fig. 3a,b). However in

Fig. 3 Transmission electron micrographs of the particle-matrix interface for the composites with oxidized SiC particles

- a) AS7G03
- b) 6061

AS7G03, the amount of Mg is only 0.3% so that spinel formation removes Mg from the matrix thus significantly impairing age-hardening. In the case of 6061, since Mg concentration is greater than in AS7G03, spinel formation does not greatly affect Mg₂Si precipitation leading to approximately the same hardening behaviour as for as-received SiC particles except for the peak hardness which seems to occur at later times. The explanation for this phenomenon is not known. The behaviour of the 6061 composite containing oxidized particles can be compared with that obtained in a AS7G03 composite in which 1% Mg was put in addition to the normal 0.3%. In this material indeed, the age hardening behaviours are the same for as-received and oxidized particles (6).

Fig. 3b shows that, in addition to spinel, Mg_2Si is present at the particle-matrix interface. This phase was also observed at the interface of non-oxidized particles which suggests that it is not only due to the rejection of Si during the formation of $MgAl_2O_4$. Moreover, since the photomicrograph corresponds to the solution-treated condition, this phase is formed during solidification and does not dissolve during solution heat-treatment.

The SiC particles act then as nucleants for Mg_2Si which probably make this phase more stable against dissolution. Such an heterogeneous nucleation is normal owing to the usual rejection of the SiC particles by the solidifying Al-rich dendrites which leads to segregation in the last freezing liquid. The situation is the same for AS7G03 composites which show Si attached to the SiC particles (fig. 3a).

TEM observations thus show that oxidized particles lead to spinel formation at the particle-matrix interfaces. Since the interfaces play an important role in the behaviour of a composite material, these reaction products can influence greatly the mechanical properties particularly in tension during which either rupture of the particles or decohesion at the particle-matrix interfaces can occur. In-situ SEM tensile test experiments were performed by Da Silva and Bretheau using the same materials as for this investigation and the results are presented in this conference (11).

CONCLUSION

The addition of SiC particles to the AS7G03 and 6061 aluminium alloys changes the kinetics of age hardening in a way which depends on the aging temperature. This phenomenon can be explained by the thermal mismatch between the reinforcement and the matrix and by the presence of a high density of interfaces which lowers quenched-in vacancy concentration thus inhibiting GP zone formation. The surfacic nature of the particles also changes the aging behaviour of the composite and this effects is clearly visible in alloys containing a low amount of Mg like AS7G03. Indeed spinel formation at the interfaces leads to Mg depletion in the matrix thus impairing age hardening.

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after addition, reheating up to 700°C and pouring into the preheated mould ($\approx 300^\circ\text{C}$) of a squeeze-casting apparatus which allows solidification to be accomplished under a pressure of about 100 MPa. Particle size was 13 μm and 10 volume percents particles were used in these experiments. The SiC particles were used either in the as-received condition or after an oxidation in air for two hours at 1100°C. The average thickness of the oxide layer was measured by Auger spectroscopy and found to be about 50 nm and 500 nm respectively (6). Specimens of the matrix alloys and the composites were solutionized at 540°C for eight hours for AS7G03 (at 520°C for 2h for 6061) water quenched then aged isothermally for various times at several temperatures. Hardness measurements were performed at room temperature just after air cooling from the aging temperature using a ball of 2.5 mm with a load of 625 N. 5 readings were usually taken for each specimen in order to eliminate possible segregation effects. Microstructural observations were carried out with a JEOL 200 CX transmission electron microscope. Samples were prepared by conventional grinding and final ion milling in argon at 4 kV, 50 μA and 20° impingement angle.

RESULTS

The variation with aging time of the Brinell hardness of the AS7G03 alloy and the composites with as-received particles is shown in Fig. 1 a, b and c for different aging temperatures. The aging behaviours of the matrix alloy and the composites are very similar whatever the aging temperature, hardness increasing initially with increasing time, up to a maximum beyond which it decreases with further increase of the aging time. Also the peak hardness is reached in less time at higher aging temperature for both the matrix alloy and the composite. However at low aging temperature (120°C), the matrix alloy seems to age faster than the composite whereas the inverse is observed at high aging temperature (185°C). At 140°C, the peak hardness of both materials occurs approximately at the same time.

Fig. 1 Aging characteristics of the matrix AS7G03 and the composites
 a) at 120°C
 b) at 140°C
 c) at 185°C